

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF PARENTAL RESPONSIBILITY IN THE FAMILY

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ABSTRACT

The article examines various psychological and pedagogical approaches to raising children in a family and discusses the important mechanisms of raising children today. The problem of responsible parenting has highlighted psychological views on its components.

The relevance and necessity of family education is relevant for all disciplines. State policy is aimed at increasing the birth rate of children, reducing their number, distribution to foster and foster families, and the provision of various material and housing benefits. At the same time, statistics determine the number of divorces, unregistered, single-parent families, families of the "risk group", orphans whose parents survived. Despite the socio-demographic achievements of recent years, the family has lost its significance as the basis of socialization and individual life, although this decision in the family is made by the parents, the child lays the foundation for his health and development, the worldview of the individual, is formed.

The natural developing social factor of these traditional values is the family. Through the family, the state has the opportunity to have better opportunities for

ongoing and social change. Currently, the term "responsible parenting" is quite common in literature and websites for parents interested in raising and developing their own children. Due to different interpretations of this concept, to begin with, we define the semantic characteristics of the term under study. In the dictionary of S.I. Ozhegova "responsible" is interpreted as responsible (the need, the obligation to give account of their actions, actions); vested with rights and obligations in the implementation of any activity; having a highly developed sense of duty, jealous of his duties. "Parents are father and mother in relation to their children" [10]. Despite the fact that the concept of "parenting" occurs quite often, in the scientific literature it is not clearly defined. For example, I.S. Kohn considers it from the point of view of dependence on ethnic characteristics [6], G.G. Filippova - as a parental need-motivational sphere of fatherhood and

motherhood, including a set of value orientations, views, positions, a sense of responsibility [14]. The concept of S.P. Akunina, who considers responsible parenting as an integral psychological education of a person, including a set of parental orientations, attitudes and expectations, parental feelings, attitudes, attitudes and beliefs regarding oneself as a parent. Responsible parenting is understood as spiritually the moral and social need of the individual and its orientation towards the value education of children, to positive, cognitive, emotional, behavioral relationships in the family, subjective feeling of being a parent, effective interaction in the family and the formation of value attitudes of parenting [2].

According to V.N. Druzhinin, parental responsibility includes responsibility to society and to one's conscience, and also determines the behavior of the parent [5]. V.D. Moskalenko notes that a responsible parent is able to form a high level of self-esteem in a child, love and self-acceptance, showing by his own example that each person is worthy of respect [9].

R.M.Chumicheva proposes to consider "responsible parenting" as a social phenomenon that characterizes the qualities of parents, manifested in the relationships and interactions between parents and children (care, respect, support, sympathy, empathy). At the same time, the child is the absolute value of education, and humanity in relation to the child is the pinnacle of parental morality (love, mercy, kindness, empathy, altruism, willingness to help those close and distant, understanding the value and uniqueness of each person, the inviolability of human life,

the ability to exercise tolerance and benevolence) [15].

An interesting point of view is M.G. Korolev, who defines parenting as integral social and psychological education of the individual, including a set of value orientations of the parent, attitudes and expectations, parental feelings, attitudes and positions, parental responsibility and the style of family education. Building responsible parenting involves two aspects:

a) the formation of parenting as a means of raising a child,

b) the formation of parenting as a special case,

socialization of the child in the field of transmission of ideas about family roles, parenting and marital functions [7]. M. Rastin identified the following aspects of responsible parenting: responsibility for the weaker, correction of one's own destructive behavior, inclusion in the life of children [11]. T.E.Shaposhnikova highlighted the conditions under which family members are able to create such a "type of relationship that helps to reveal their potential, leads to a change and development of personality, personal growth":

1) frankness and sincerity in relation to oneself;

2) acceptance of a person, recognition of his unconditional value as an individual, regardless of his specific state, behavior and feelings;

3) understanding of a person, subtle empathy for each feeling and expression, inadmissibility of assessments [16].

M. Merolaeva considers responsible parenting as a balance of different sides education:

communicative side (regular communication with the child);

- Emotional side (avoidance of evaluations in judgments and condemnation, motivation in the child to respond reactions, giving him the opportunity to discuss problems and share his experiences);
- Economic side (the parent must be able to pay for the child's education, provide his necessary clothing, everything necessary);
- protective side (preservation and strengthening of the child's health, including psychological);
- normative side (the parent needs to act as a translator of the stereotype of behavior for the child must be taught to follow the rules established by society);
- the spiritual side (the ability to instill in a child basic life values) [8].

Based on the above, it is possible to define the tasks of responsible parenting: preserving health and life of the child; material support; joint leisure activities, pastime through communication; prevention of the development of addictions in children by developing spiritual and moral components, creating a trusting environment in the family; the ability to provide support and protection in difficult situations; to teach the child by their own example of perseverance and perseverance, to instill hard work and love for learning [4].

Factors that determine responsible parenting: intergenerational continuity; the presence of both parents; satisfaction with marriage and relationships in it; joint leisure and interests of parents; spiritual

and moral well-being of the family; attentive attitude to the state of health of family members; social, household, material well-being; the absence of chronic family conflicts between parents and children, in the marital subsystem, between generations; unified approach to education a child on the part of both parents; a healthy family life - only by their example can parents instill in a child a love for sports and good habits [8]. A number of authors note that parental roles and feelings should qualitatively change depending on the child's age (number of children) [13]. This was pointed out by K. Rogers, who described the stages of parental responsibility for their child: the first stage presupposes constant, full responsibility; at the second stage, parents begin to say "no" to their child due to the fact that his mind and the ability to separate what is forbidden from what is allowed are already awakening in him; at the third stage, parents begin to interact with their child, offering an explanation "no, because ...". If the first step is passed, then the child has grown up, has become independent and no longer needs the care of the family. In the opposite case, the so-called symbiotic relationship with the child (most often with the mother) will complicate not only his exit into an autonomous life, but also the possibility of forming his own family. Some children are educated only in the "not allowed" register. This severely limits the development of the child. Transitions from one stage to another depend on the rapidity of the child's mental development [12]. At the same time, the parents themselves consider the main feature of responsible parenting to be the preservation of the child's health and life. At the same time, 23.8% of fathers believe that

useful books will largely help to form responsible parenting, and 33.3% of mothers assign this role to consultations with a psychologist. Moreover, according to the data research "Responsible Parenting in the Modern World" by the Institute of Sociology of Sciences, 65% of women and 54% of men with children identified themselves as responsible parents.

In modern Russian society, the following trends in parental attitudes toward problem:

1) the belief that to become a full-fledged parent is not enough just to give birth to a child, it is necessary to expand maternal and paternal competences by educating specialists or more experienced parents.

2) attitude to parenting as an important, socially responsible business, the effectiveness of which depends on the extent to which the mother and father are aware of and accept this responsibility.

3) meaningful filling of parental education, which is often limited to the elaboration of issues of health culture and perinatal psychology at the stage of pregnancy.

4) activation of parental initiative in resisting any external standards in relation to ideas about which health-improving, upbringing, educational practices can be considered normative [1].

With the importance and relevance of a purposeful approach to the formation of a culture of responsible parenting, it must be emphasized that it is completely unacceptable to try to fit the specific features of the upbringing of each family under any one standard option. Any programs for the purposeful formation of a culture of parenting, training of parents should be purely voluntary and assume variability of models. In conclusion, it seems relevant to cite the statement of P.P. Blonsky [3] "Education is a difficult matter only as long as we want, without educating ourselves, to raise our children or anyone else. If you understand that we can educate others only through ourselves, then the question of upbringing is eliminated and one question remains: how should one live? "

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